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**SOCIO-LEGAL AND OTHER CAUSES OF THE DEFORMATION OF THE JUDGE'S
 LEGAL CONSCIOUSNESS**

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the concept and content of a judge’s legal consciousness and the causes and manifestations of its deformation. The main goal of the study is to identify the social, psychological, institutional, and legal factors that contribute to the deformation of a judge’s professional legal awareness. The work analyzes the perspectives of legal scholars, psychologists, and sociologists, incorporating both national and international viewpoints. Case examples from judicial practice help to clarify the mechanisms of maintaining or distorting legal consciousness. The findings emphasize the need for effective preventive measures against the deformation of legal consciousness.

Keywords: judge, legal consciousness, deformation, legal culture, professional awareness, judicial practice, social factors, psychological influence.

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**SUDYANING HUQUQIY ONGI DEFORMATSIYASINING IJTIMOIIY-HUQUQIY VA
 BOSHQA SABABLARI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada sudya huquqiy ongi tushunchasi, uning mazmun-mohiyati va deformatsiyalanish holatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – sudya huquqiy ongining buzilishi (deformatsiyasi)ga olib keluvchi ijtimoiy, psixologik, institutsional va huquqiy omillarni aniqlashdir. Maqolada huquqshunos, psixolog va sotsiologlarning tegishli ilmiy qarashlari, shu jumladan, milliy va xorijiy olimlar nuqtai nazarlari tahlil qilinadi. Sud amaliyotida uchraydigan holatlar orqali huquqiy ongni saqlash yoki buzilish jarayonlariga aniqlik kiritiladi. Ilmiy natijalar huquqiy ong deformatsiyasiga qarshi ta’sirchan profilaktika choralarini ko’rish zarurligini asoslaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: sudya, huquqiy ong, deformatsiya, huquqiy madaniyat, kasbiy ong, sud amaliyoti, ijtimoiy omil, psixologik ta’sir.

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СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВЫЕ И ДРУГИЕ ПРИЧИНЫ ДЕФОРМАЦИИ ПРАВОВОГО СОЗНАНИЯ СУДЬИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется концепция правового сознания судьи, его содержание и случаи деформации. Основная цель исследования – выявление социальных, психологических, институциональных и правовых факторов, приводящих к искажению (деформации) правового сознания судьи. В статье анализируются соответствующие научные взгляды юристов, психологов и социологов, в том числе взгляды отечественных и зарубежных ученых. Процессы сохранения или нарушения правового сознания уточняются на примере ситуаций, встречающихся в судебной практике. Научные результаты обосновывают необходимость принятия эффективных профилактических мер против деформации правового сознания.

Ключевые слова: судья, правовое сознание, деформация, правовая культура, профессиональное сознание, судебная практика, социальный фактор, психологическое воздействие.

In any democratic legal society, the personality of a judge is entrusted with great responsibility. A judge should not only be a specialist who knows the laws, but also a person who is faithful to the principles of justice and makes impartial decisions. The basis for this is a highly developed and correctly formed legal consciousness. Because the improvement of legal consciousness and legal culture in society is one of the most important conditions for ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legality. Therefore, the correct formation of a judge's legal consciousness is of decisive importance in the implementation of judicial justice.

Unfortunately, in practical life there are sometimes cases where the legal mind of judges is deformed. That is, the judge's views and values regarding law change and begin to withdraw from the positive content, which lowers the quality of serving justice. Such a violation of the judge's legal mind has a negative impact not only on the unfairness of individual decisions, but also on the general legality. As a result, citizens' trust in the courts and laws may weaken, crimes may increase, and the reputation of the judiciary may decrease. Therefore, studying the causes of the deformation of the judge's legal consciousness and eliminating them is an urgent task in building a society with a high legal culture.

This article clarifies the concept of the judge's legal consciousness and the terms of its deformation. Also, relevant scientific views of legal scientists, sociologists and psychologists are analyzed, and socio-legal, psychological, criminological and other reasons for the deformation of the judge's legal consciousness are comprehensively explained. In the process of analysis, local (national) and foreign sources were relied on, and how this problem was approached in the experience of different countries was also considered.

Legal consciousness is understood as the set of ideas and feelings that people have about law, legislation, law and order, and other legal phenomena. In simpler terms, legal consciousness is a person's attitude to laws and justice, his ideas about rights and duties. Legal consciousness forms the basis of legal culture in society, and its high level is manifested in such virtues as respect for laws and refraining from violations of the law. In theory, a violation of legal consciousness can manifest itself in various forms. For example, legal nihilism is a state of denial of laws and disregard for the requirements of the law, while legal idealism is a tendency to consider laws as absolute documents that immediately solve all problems. Both situations, in fact, arise as a result of an imbalance in legal

consciousness and lead to a lack of legal knowledge and culture. Thus, the lack of development or incorrect formation of legal consciousness leads to its deformation (i.e., distortion) [1].

The concept of deformation of legal consciousness is defined differently by scientists. In a general sense, the deformation of legal consciousness is its “change for the worse”, that is, the negative trend in the views of citizens on the law, and this change negatively affects society as a whole. As a result of such deformation in a broad sense, respect for the law in individuals decreases, and the desire to comply with legal requirements decreases.

As for the deformation of the professional legal consciousness of a judge, this term is clearly defined in legal theory. In particular, according to the definition of R.A. Kuznetsov, the deformation of the professional legal consciousness of a lawyer (including a judge) is understood as a change in the characteristics of the legal personality and his professional abilities in an asocial direction [5]. Such changes occur in connection with certain factors in the process of formation of the legal personality, as well as the content, organization and conditions of his professional activity. That is, the change in the personal characteristics and professional abilities of a judge in an unfriendly, antisocial direction is considered a violation of his legal consciousness.

If we approach the topic from a socio-philosophical and criminological point of view, it becomes clear that the deformation of legal consciousness is an integral part of the deviations leading to a crime. For example, as the science of criminology notes, the deformation of legal consciousness is an element of the mechanism of criminal behavior. Persons with deformed legal consciousness do not fully understand their responsibility to society, do not respect the law, and this situation predisposes them to destructive (criminal) behavior. For such persons, breaking the law is not “dirty”, but rather becomes a habit, and they may even begin to morally justify their actions. Of course, although judges do not directly belong to the category of criminals, a sharp violation of legal consciousness can also lead them to a spirit of disrespect for the law. Therefore, it is very important to study the conditions under which a judge’s deformation of legal consciousness occurs and to develop measures to prevent it [2].

From the analysis of various scientific sources, it became clear that the deformation of a judge's legal consciousness can be caused by various factors - social, legal, institutional, psychological and personal factors. These reasons are described below by category.

Socio-legal reasons: The formation of a judge's legal consciousness is primarily influenced by the broader social environment and legal system. If the general level of legal culture in society is low, this can also affect the judge. For example, the lack of legal knowledge and legal education causes legal nihilism not only among ordinary citizens, but sometimes also among civil servants. As legal scholars have noted, the low level of legal consciousness and culture among the population also affects the legal culture of officials, and in such conditions, disregard for the law may arise in persons performing their duties.

Especially during periods of major social changes, the deformation of legal consciousness can intensify. For example, as noted by Russian scientists, during the political and economic reforms, there was a decline in the prestige of the law, a decrease in the authority of the judiciary and law enforcement agencies; as a result, the trust in the rule of law has weakened while the society's demand and need for law enforcement agencies has increased. Also, due to socio-economic instability and criminalization of public life, there is a negative impact on the practice of law enforcement, and cases of violation of legal views and disrespect for the law have been observed among legal professionals. In other words, if the rule of law weakens in society, it creates an environment that directly affects the minds of judges [3].

Another important socio-legal factor related to this is the weakening of legal control and public oversight. If effective public control and transparency over the activities of judges are not ensured, over time, judges may behave as if they are not accountable to society. Psychologist E.P. Ilyin indicates that one of the reasons for the deterioration of the consciousness of judges is “the difficulty of limiting power, the lack of public control and criticism” [4]. Because always being in the position of “ruler” in front of the victim and the parties, not hearing criticism from anyone, can cause a judge to feel like a special category. This gradually leads to the deterioration of legal consciousness

- for example, a tendency not to put the law above oneself. From this point of view, open debates in society regarding judges, healthy criticism of the media, and the presence of civil society control serve to position judges as true guardians of the law.

Institutional and professional reasons: Internal factors of the judicial system also have a strong impact on the legal consciousness of a judge. If there is a shortage of personnel in the system, an increase in workload, low material resources, or other organizational problems, these circumstances lead to professional deformation in the judge. For example, in scientific literature, it is noted that in conditions of a small number of judges and excessive workload, a judge has to deal with the same, similar subject matter every day for many years. Such monotonous and long-lasting work increases apathy, lethargy, and dissatisfaction with work in a judge. As a result, the desire for novelty in work weakens, and a creative approach to work is replaced by superficiality. Scientific studies have noted that as a result of monotonous professional activity, negative characteristics such as pessimism, negativism, decreased working capacity, loss of interest in work, and a fading desire to update professional knowledge are formed in judges. Of course, these signs are clear signals that the judge's legal consciousness is being deformed.

Another institutional problem is related to the system of appointment and professional development of judges. If the selection processes are not organized fairly, and not capable and responsible personnel, but random individuals due to acquaintances or other illegal factors, become judges, such a system itself encourages legal ignorance. Also, the weakening of the system of continuous training and professional development of judges during their service, in particular, updating their legal knowledge and enriching their ethical and psychological knowledge, can also increase deformation. On the contrary, it is known that in the experience of developed countries, when appointing judges and constantly evaluating them, a system has been established that takes into account not only legal knowledge, but also psychological stability, personal values, and moral character. In particular, in Russia, when selecting candidates for judges, special psychological tests are conducted to determine the candidate's mental stability, lack of delusions, asocial views, or motives based solely on personal interest. This ensures that unsuitable individuals do not enter the profession and that future judges are people who can withstand various stressful situations and are not prone to greed or bribery for their own benefit. If such strict requirements are not imposed on the selection of candidates for judges, there is a risk that individuals who put their personal interests above the rule of law will enter the judicial corps. When such people take office, they will actually begin to serve their own interests, not the law - that is, they will operate with a deformed legal consciousness. Therefore, the correct selection of personnel is an important institutional measure to prevent deformation.

In this context, the conditions that ensure the independence of the judge are also important in preventing deformation. If external parties do not interfere with the judge's independent decision-making in accordance with the law, his legal consciousness will develop in accordance with his duties. However, on the contrary, judges who are forced to make decisions under pressure from other officials or higher authorities may lose confidence in the fairness of their decisions and develop legal distrust. For example, inconsistencies and ambiguities in the laws cause a judge to be unsure and hesitant about the correct application of the law, which over time can turn into doubt and even disrespect for the law in the judge. Therefore, institutional factors such as the clarity and stability of legal norms and the absence of unjustified interference in the activities of judges are also recognized as reasons that directly affect the healthy preservation of the judge's legal consciousness.

Psychological reasons: The profession of a judge is an activity that constantly encounters uncompromising situations, conflicting parties, and serious criminal cases, and puts great pressure on mental processes. Therefore, psychological stability is considered necessary to prevent significant stress and changes in the judge's psyche, otherwise professional deformation will occur. Psychologists have identified a number of psychological factors that lead to deformation in the personality of a judge. In particular, as a result of working under high stress for a long time, judges may experience nervous exhaustion (burnout). Studies have shown that judges working under high psychological pressure may experience a decrease in the speed of decision-making, a weakening of objectivity, and

even "partially illegal approaches" under the influence of an emotional state. Thus, a stressed judge may be inclined to make a rash decision in order to get out of the situation faster, instead of making a calm and fair decision, or in some cases, may make an unjust decision under the influence of his emotions [6].

Also, after mental stress, judges experience various cognitive deficits and changes in their perceptions. For example, a judge who constantly sees crimes and violations in his daily work may develop a general distrust of people. Some psychological studies have shown that excessive cynicism (pessimism) towards life and people in judges is one of the signs of professional deformation. Because a judge constantly deals with criminals and litigants, over time he may begin to perceive all people as a category that seeks only their own interests and is ready to violate the law. This is a serious psychological factor leading to bias. Among the psychological reasons, a feeling of disempowerment is particularly noteworthy. That is, a judge may become accustomed to the fact that for several years he always acts in a leading role (like a "khan") and everyone is looking to his word. This situation leads not only to the loss of personal humility, but also to the feeling of being not a slave to the laws, but a superior from a spiritual point of view. In scientific literature, this situation is described by such forms of deformation as "professional egocentrism" (for example, an official begins to place himself above the law, etc.). Having this in mind, E.P. Ilyin emphasizes the importance of the ability for judges to voluntarily analyze themselves and accept healthy criticism; he said that a judge should have a special quality of healthy self-criticism [4]. If a judge does not have this quality, he becomes a type of person who does not like criticism, does not admit his mistakes, and acts as he sees fit. This accelerates the deterioration of his legal consciousness.

Of course, not every judge may experience such negative psychological changes. It has been found that judges with high personal psychological stability, who can manage stress, have strong internal integrity (strong spiritual integrity) and internal motivation are more likely to not be subject to such deformations. In world experience, it is precisely such qualities - the ability to manage stress, overcome emotional stress, and adhere to the principle of justice - that are recognized as factors ensuring the stability of a judge's legal consciousness. Therefore, in the process of selecting and training judges in foreign countries, special attention is paid to their psychological profile, nervous stability, internal motivation and human values. Psychologically mature and stable judges are able to maintain their legal consciousness in a healthy state, despite the various stresses and pressures that arise during their professional activities.

Personal and moral reasons: The deformation of a judge's legal consciousness is associated not only with the influence of external factors, but also with personal and moral qualities. If a judge's personal value system is incorrectly formed, for example, if he is a person who puts personal interests first rather than the rule of law, then the legal consciousness of such persons is weak from the very beginning and, depending on the situation, is quickly destroyed. In many cases, if the spiritual characteristics of a candidate for a judge are ignored, this deficiency will manifest itself later. For example, if a person has a tendency to bribery, a penchant for abuse of power, and a disregard for people, such people should not be brought close to the judiciary. Otherwise, such judges will quickly give in to interests not provided for by law and push aside the principles of justice [7].

Therefore, it is not without reason that a procedure for psychological and psychiatric examination of candidates for the position of judge was introduced: not only the mental state of the candidate, but also his moral values are checked, and it is determined whether there are any asocial or greedy individuals. For example, Russian researchers E.V. Dvortsova and E.V. Litvinenko studied professional deformation of prosecutors and defined it as "a change in the psychological structure of a person in the process of professional activity and the transfer of this changed professional behavior to life outside of work" [1.S. 43]. Thus, if negative traits in a person begin to manifest themselves not only at work, but also in his personal life, this indicates a deepening deformation. For example, if a judge disregards the laws even in an environment outside of work, considers lawbreaking to be commonplace, and even treats his relatives unfairly, this means that his legal consciousness has fundamentally shifted. Unfortunately, such situations are usually clearly manifested in cases where a judge engages in corruption and uses his office to obtain illegal benefits. Lack of moral strength is an

important personal reason leading to deformation. If a judge has a weak sense of conscience and fairness, he will only fulfill the requirements of the law in words and look for ways to circumvent them in practice. For example, a judge may allow nepotism in a case due to his closeness to some parties or deviate from justice in order to satisfy requests for acquaintances. Such defects are evidence of weak moral values, and in this case, a dangerous concept is formed in the judge's mind that "the law is for everyone, but not for some people." In scientific literature, it has been noted that such a deviation of legal consciousness takes the form of "legal infantilism" (legal childhood) or "double standard" (double application of the law). That is, a person comes to believe that even though he knows the law, he can still violate it. Therefore, the personal upbringing and spiritual maturity of judges are the main shield against deformation. Because a judge with a high internal culture and conscientious behavior will be able to refrain from disregarding the law or violating the rules for his own benefit in any situation.

The reasons mentioned above show what factors cause the deformation of a judge's legal consciousness. The analysis shows that objective (social-institutional) factors and subjective (psychological-moral) factors are closely related in this process. For example, a low level of legal culture in society (objective factor) can weaken a judge's personal legal consciousness; on the contrary, a judge's personal greed (subjective factor) reduces public trust in the entire judicial body. Therefore, a comprehensive approach is necessary in understanding the problem of deformation. Scientific sources also emphasize that objective and subjective factors cannot be separated from each other, they act together. Therefore, in order to solve the problem, it is necessary to pay equal attention to both sides. International experience shows that systematic measures are required to maintain a healthy legal consciousness of judges. First of all, it is important to introduce strict ethical standards and control mechanisms for the judicial corps. Many countries have adopted Codes of Ethics for Judges, which provide that actions that contradict the principles of fair trial for judges are considered as initial signs of deformation. For example, the Bangalore Principles adopted by the UN strictly define principles such as independence, impartiality, and impartiality of judges. Deviation from these principles is considered a sign of deformation, and in such cases, disciplinary measures are taken against the judge. At the same time, a very important issue is the psychological support of judges. In some developed countries, psychological counseling services have been established for judges, and they can participate in programs aimed at managing stress and alleviating emotional stress. Studies show that providing psychological support to judges helps prevent professional burnout and thereby ensure the stability of their legal consciousness [8].

Another important aspect of the fight against deformation is personnel training and legal education. As noted above, when selecting candidates for judges, it is necessary to take into account not only knowledge, but also their personal qualities. Scientists have also suggested that current judges should be kept informed of new developments in the field of law through regular retraining courses and "immunized" their legal consciousness. For example, through behavioral training and seminars on ethical leadership for judges, it is possible to prevent undesirable tendencies that may arise in judges at an early stage. Criminological studies also show that increasing the level of legal culture and education among the population reduces crime and is the main means of eliminating violations of legal consciousness. Therefore, the formation of an atmosphere of legal literacy and respect for the law in the social environment in which judges operate is also of vital importance.

From the above, it can be seen that in the experience of various countries, measures are being taken to prevent the deformation of the legal consciousness of judges, such as strengthening the legislative framework (for example, increasing guarantees of judicial independence), improving the system of selection and certification of judges, and providing them with comprehensive support during their service. For example, in recent years, Uzbekistan has adopted a code of ethics for judges and implemented state programs aimed at raising legal awareness and culture in society. These reforms are intended to ensure strict adherence to legality by judges and strengthen citizens' trust in the courts [9].

It turned out that the deformation of the judge's legal consciousness is a complex socio-legal phenomenon caused by many factors. The analysis presented in the article shows that there are the following main reasons for the deformation:

Socio-legal factors: insufficient formation of the legal culture and rule of law system in the society, the decline in the reputation of the law as a result of transition periods and instability, the existence of legal nihilism in the population and the decrease of trust in the judicial authorities have a negative impact on the mind of the judge. In such conditions, judges may also fall into a spirit of disrespect for the law.

Institutional and professional factors: the internal shortcomings of the judicial system - shortage of personnel, excessive workload, low financial incentives, inconsistencies in promotion - increase the feeling of professional burnout (fatigue) and job dissatisfaction among judges. Long years of monotonous work can lead to pessimism and apathy, while the lack of criticism and control can strengthen self-confidence. Also, the failure to take into account moral and psychological criteria in the system of selecting and evaluating judges can lead to the emergence of greedy or irresponsible individuals among the appointed personnel.

Psychological factors: Due to the high stress and mental pressure inherent in the profession of a judge, some individuals may experience emotional exhaustion, professional burnout, and even a breakdown in legal awareness. Under stress, it becomes difficult to maintain impartiality, and attention and analytical skills weaken. Constantly being in an environment of crime and conflict during work can form a cynical attitude towards humanity in a judge. As a result of cognitive disorders, the judge is at increased risk of one-sided perception of reality and stereotypical views. If such psychological problems are not given sufficient attention, the judge's loyalty to the law will suffer [10].

Personal and moral factors: the judge's own values and level of conscientiousness are also decisive factors. If a person has a tendency to prioritize personal interests over law and justice, he may not be able to maintain a healthy legal awareness even under ideal conditions. Deformation quickly deepens in judges prone to bribery, nepotism, and abuse of office. Such individuals seek ways to circumvent laws, allow irregularities, and as a result, operate contrary to the principles of fair trial. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that the moral integrity and honesty of a judge are the most important “antidote” to deformation.

In conclusion, the fight against the deformation of the legal consciousness of judges requires a comprehensive approach. External reforms alone or an emphasis on personal responsibility alone are not enough. It is necessary to simultaneously improve both the legal system and measures aimed at developing the personality of judges. In this regard, the following recommendations arise:

1. **Improve the legal environment:** it is necessary to make legislation clear and understandable, fully guarantee the independence of judges, and completely stop illegal interference in court decisions. Only if judges act in practice according to the law and their conscience, their legal consciousness will remain at a high level.

2. **Improve personnel policy:** when selecting candidates for judges, their psychology and moral character should be carefully studied. When appointing judges, familiarity and other influences should be limited. It is also important to periodically assess the qualifications of current judges and involve them in retraining courses.

3. **Psychological support:** during the period of service for judges, it is necessary to organize psychological training, counseling, and programs aimed at preventing burnout. It helps judges manage their emotions and stress and protects their legal minds.

4. **Moral education and legal culture:** raising legal awareness and culture among judges and society as a whole should be a constant task. Each judge should work on himself, strive to educate himself, and get used to listening to public criticism. If the general legal environment in society improves by popularizing legal knowledge and increasing the public's respect for the law, this will directly have a positive impact on the judicial system. In conclusion, the reasons that cause the deformation of a judge's legal consciousness are multifaceted, and in order to fully understand them, it is necessary to conduct research at the intersection of the disciplines of law, sociology, psychology,

and ethics. The analytical conclusions presented in this article show that early identification of the factors that cause deformation and taking measures to prevent them will ensure that judges remain true to the rules of justice in the performance of their duties. This, in turn, is the main guarantee of strengthening the rule of law in society and citizens' trust in justice.

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ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

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